

PARENTS' SUPPORT, LEARNERS' MOTIVATIONAL PRACTICES AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE ON BLENDED LEARNING IN MAPEH

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ABSTRACT

The main purpose of the study was to determine the parents' support learners' motivational practices and academic performance of the Grade VI pupils of the Third Congressional District for the academic year 2022-2023. This further sought to verify the relationship of parental support to MAPEH VI academic performance and motivational learner to MAPEH VI academic performance. Furthermore, it sought to determine the relationship between the parents' profile and the MAPEH VI academic performance. This study employed the descriptive study design in the relationship between the mentioned variables. The data gathered were treated, analyzed and interpreted through the average percentage formula, weighted mean, spearman rank coefficient and chi-square. It shows that Parents' support has a significant relationship with the learners' academic performance in MAPEH VI. In addition, the motivational practices of the learners have no significant relationship between the academic performances in MAPEH VI. Moreover, the parent profile, highest educational attainment, gross monthly income and occupation manifest significant relationship to the academic performance. Thus, a campaign and encouragement for parental support is needed to come up with good results in learners' academic performance. A proposed training design suggests that the District Supervisor may look into the possibility of providing opportunities of conducting training and seminars on how parents can support their children in their academic activities. The school heads may encourage the teachers to see the Action plan for the plan for the suggested activities for seminars in parental support. Finally, other researchers may conduct aligned studies on the factors that may affect the learners' academic performance in the study.

Keywords: *Academic Performance, Blended Learning, Learners' Motivational Practices, Parents' Support, and MAPEH VI*

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly transformed education delivery systems worldwide, with the Philippines undergoing one of the most significant shifts. The traditional face-to-face learning model has given way to various forms of distance and blended learning, a shift initiated by the Department of Education (DepEd) to ensure educational continuity. This transition has placed unprecedented emphasis on the role of parents and guardians in their children's learning, particularly during home-based instruction. Parents have emerged as crucial facilitators in ensuring students remain engaged, motivated, and able to navigate learning, especially in subjects that traditionally rely on hands-on, interactive methods such as Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health (MAPEH).

Blended learning, as introduced by DepEd, merges in-person instruction with home-based activities, combining printed modules and online resources. This approach aims to preserve the benefits of traditional classroom settings while incorporating the flexibility of distance learning. According to Whitley, Beauchamp, and Brown (2021), blended learning offers advantages over fully home-based learning by providing richer teacher-student interactions, peer collaboration, and more structured educational experiences. Nonetheless, the success of this model hinges significantly on the active participation of parents in supervising and guiding their children through the home-based portions of the curriculum. For students in MAPEH, this role becomes even more critical, as the subject's participatory and practical nature can be challenging to execute without the right home environment and parental support.

As emphasized by Parojenog (2020), teachers aim for their instructional practices to be effective and impactful for all students, particularly in fostering parental support and enhancing learners' motivational practices, which are crucial for academic performance in blended learning environments, such as in MAPEH. MAPEH, focusing on physical activity, artistic expression, and health education, presents unique challenges when adapted to blended learning. In face-to-face settings, students benefit from real-time guidance and collaboration, crucial for subjects like music and physical education, where immediate feedback is key. Home-based learning, however, places more responsibility on students to self-regulate and sustain their engagement. This is where parental involvement becomes a determining factor in whether students can successfully navigate these challenges. Parents are expected to foster a supportive learning environment, help students with learning modules, and encourage participation in home-based activities to ensure continued progress in subjects like MAPEH.

The Philippine government has recognized the importance of parents' involvement in this setup. When blended learning was approved by the President and implemented in low-risk areas, parents were required to provide consent, underscoring their role in the process. Schools that participated in the pilot implementation of blended learning allowed for a hybrid model with a few days of face-to-face instruction, followed by home-based learning on other days. This system aimed to strike a balance between educational needs and health concerns amidst the pandemic. The active role of parents, especially in

monitoring and supporting students during home-based learning, became critical to the success of this modality.

DepEd Order No. 34, s. 2022, further formalized blended learning as a core strategy for ensuring educational continuity. This policy emphasized creating flexible learning environments and highlighted the crucial role of parents in making blended learning successful, particularly for students in remote areas. Parents were tasked with helping children stay on track with learning modules and assignments, ensuring that they could focus and engage with the material despite the distractions of home environments. These expectations have put considerable pressure on parents, many of whom balance full-time work and other responsibilities with their new roles as co-educators.

The involvement of parents in blended learning can be further understood through the lens of Deci and Ryan's Self-Determination Theory, which posits that students' motivation is driven by the satisfaction of three basic psychological needs: autonomy, competence, and relatedness. In the context of blended learning, autonomy is fostered when students are empowered to take charge of their learning at home. Competence is enhanced when parents provide the necessary guidance and support to help students succeed in their academic tasks. Relatedness is maintained through the connections students can continue to have with their peers and teachers, supported by parents. The involvement of parents, particularly in the home-based aspects of blended learning, is crucial in ensuring that these psychological needs are met, keeping students motivated and engaged.

Research supports the positive impact of parental involvement on academic performance and motivation. Pomerantz and Brooks (2017) found that children whose parents are actively involved in their education tend to exhibit higher levels of motivation and perform better academically. This is especially relevant for subjects like MAPEH, where practical application and consistent participation are key to mastery. Parents who provide encouragement, structure, and resources create a home environment conducive to learning, enabling students to remain motivated and succeed even in challenging circumstances.

However, this shift has not been without its difficulties. Parents have found themselves navigating a multitude of new responsibilities, including overseeing learning schedules, helping with assignments, and maintaining a suitable learning environment at home. For many, this has added stress to their already demanding lives, especially in households where resources are limited or parents lack the academic skills to provide adequate support (Hara, 2000). These challenges underscore the need for additional support mechanisms for parents in the blended learning model, ensuring they are not overwhelmed by the demands of facilitating their children's education.

The focus of this study is to examine the relationship between parental support, learner motivation, and academic performance within the context of MAPEH VI blended learning. By analyzing how parental involvement influences student engagement and success, this research aims to provide valuable insights into optimizing blended learning,

particularly for subjects that require high levels of interaction and practical application. Findings from this study will contribute to the broader conversation about how blended learning can be adapted to meet the needs of both students and parents and will offer recommendations for schools and policymakers on supporting parents in their essential role within the blended learning framework.

In conclusion, the educational landscape in the Philippines continues to evolve in response to the ongoing challenges of the COVID-19 pandemic. The role of parents in blended learning, especially in subjects like MAPEH, has become vital. As students navigate this new educational setup, parental involvement in fostering motivation, creating a conducive learning environment, and supporting hands-on activities will remain essential to ensuring academic success. This study seeks to shed light on the dynamics of parental support and its impact on learners' outcomes, contributing to the ongoing efforts to improve educational practices and policies in the Philippines.

Research Questions

The main purpose of this study was to assess the parents support, learners' motivational practices and academic performance during the pilot phase in MAPEH VI of the selected parents, teachers and learners of the Public Central Elementary Schools in Third Congressional District, Division of Bohol for the School Year 2022- 2023.

Specifically, it sought to address the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the parents' respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 gender;
 - 1.3 highest educational attainment;
 - 1.4 occupation; and
 - 1.5 gross monthly income?
2. What is the level of the parents' support in the blended learning in MAPEH VI in terms of:
 - 2.1 physical support;
 - 2.2 emotional support; and
 - 2.3 financial support?
3. What is the level of the learners' motivational practices in the blended - learning in MAPEH VI in terms of:
 - 3.1 intrinsic motivation; and
 - 3.2 extrinsic motivation?
4. What is the learner's academic performance based on their average ratings in MAPEH VI subject?
5. Is there a significant relationship on the following
 - 5.1 parents' support and learners' performance in MAPEH VI;
 - 5.2 learners' motivational practices and MAPEH VI performance;
 - 5.3 parents' demographic profile and learners MAPEH VI performance?
6. What action plan could be proposed based on the result of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive survey design. The study utilized a modified questionnaire distributed through printed copies and through Google link in gathering responses of the parents, teachers and students on determining the parents' support, learners' motivational practices, and academic performance in MAPEH VI through blended learning.

Research Environment and Participants

The study was conducted in thirteen Central Elementary Public schools in the Third Congressional District of Bohol Division. The respondents were parents, teachers, and students from Grade VI as sample with the wide coverage area and the distance of every school.

A total of one thousand seven hundred seven (1,707) respondents composed with eight hundred thirty-two (832) parents, forty-three (43) MAPEH VI teachers, and eight hundred thirty-two (832) learners which comprise the subject of the study. With the following distribution below:

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No	Elementary Central Public Schools in 3 rd Congressional District Bohol Division	Parents	Teachers	Student
1	Anda	45	3	45
2	Carmen 1	49	3	49
3	Carmen 2	52	3	52
4	Dimiao	38	2	38
5	Duero	57	3	57
6	Garcia Hernandez	40	3	40
7	Jagna	120	5	120
8	Loboc	86	4	86
9	Mabini	53	3	53
10	Pilar	72	4	72
11	Sevilla	36	2	36
12	Sierra Bullones	63	3	63
13	Valencia	125	5	125
	TOTAL	832	43	832

Research Instrument

The researcher utilized a modified questionnaire based on Garbe's (2020) study, "COVID-19 and Remote Learning Experiences of Parents with Children during the Pandemic," to assess parental support. This questionnaire employed a four-point Likert scale (i.e., 4 - Always, 3 - Sometimes, 2 - Rarely, 1 - Never).

For evaluating learners' motivational practices in blended learning, the researcher used a questionnaire adapted from Fowler (2018). This instrument employed a four-point Likert scale (i.e., 4 - Strongly Agree, 3 - Agree, 2 - Disagree, 1 - Strongly Disagree).

To gather data on the average grades in MAPEH VI, the researcher used a teacher-designed questionnaire. This questionnaire featured four scales: 4 - Outstanding, 3 - Very Satisfactory, 2 - Satisfactory, and 1 - Fair.

Survey questionnaires were distributed to the respondents to collect the necessary information. The researcher instructed the respondents to answer the questions provided, and the collected data were used for analyzing and interpreting the results.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher initially secured written permission from the Dean of the College of Advanced Studies, the Campus Director of BISU Main Campus, and the Schools Division Superintendent of Bohol. A similar letter with the same purpose was sent to all School Administrators in Central Elementary Public Schools within the third congressional district.

Assistance was then sought from the school head of each participating school to facilitate the distribution of printed questionnaires and those sent via link. An Informed Consent Letter was also sent to the respondents. In adherence to social distancing protocols, the survey questionnaires were delivered and collected during the retrieval of the completed forms. To ensure the credibility of the results, the researcher provided clear instructions, which were included in the questionnaire.

Data Analysis

To determine the level of parents' support on delivery of blended-learning the weighted mean was used. After getting the weighted mean, the researcher interpreted the results using the following scale.

Scale	Interval	Description	Interpretation
4	3.25-4.00	Always	High level of support
3	2.50-3.24	Sometimes	Moderate level of support
2	1.75- 2.49	Rarely	Low level of support
1	1.00-1.74	Never	Very low level of support

To determine the level of learners' motivational practices in the blended-learning, the weighted mean was used. After getting the weighted mean, the researcher interpreted the results using the following scale.

Scale	Interval	Description	Interpretation
4	3.25-4.00	Strongly Agree	Highly practiced
3	2.50-3.24	Agree	Moderately practiced
2	1.75- 2.49	Disagree	Less practiced
1	1.00-1.74	Strongly Disagree	Not practiced

To determine the academic performance in MAPEH VI, the frequency distribution was employed. The researcher interpreted the results using the following scale.

Scale	Interval	Description
4	90-100	Outstanding
3	85-89	Very Satisfactory
2	80-84	Satisfactory
1	75-79	Fair

To determine the relationship between parents' support to MAPEH VI performance and Learner's motivation to MAPEH VI performance the Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient was used.

Further, the Chi-square Test was used to determine the significant relationship between the demographic profiles of the parents to learners MAPEH VI performance.

RESULTS

This section covers the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data.

Table 1
Profile of the Parent Respondents
N=832

Age	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Rank
26 to 35 years old	124	14.90	3
36 to 45 years old	342	41.11	1
46 to 55 years old	302	36.30	2
56 years old and above	64	7.69	4
Total	832	100.00	
Gender	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Rank
Male	106	12.74	2
Female	726	87.26	1
Total	832	100.00	
Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Rank

College Graduate	330	39.66	1
College Level	95	11.42	5
High School Graduate	146	17.55	2
High School Level	139	16.71	3
Elementary Graduate	99	11.90	4
Elementary Level	23	2.76	6
Total	832	100.00	
Occupation	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Rank
Farmer	244	29.33	2
Fisherman	2	0.24	7
Vendor	258	31.01	1
Government Employee	173	20.79	3
Private Sector	85	10.22	4
Self-Employed	17	2.04	6
Unemployed	52	6.25	5
Total	832	100.00	
Gross Monthly Income	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Rank
30,001 and above	272	32.69	1
25,001-30,000	20	2.40	6
20,001-25,000	192	23.08	2
15,001-20,000	166	19.95	3
10,001-15,000	133	15.99	4
5,000-10,000	48	5.77	5
Total	832	100.00	

In terms of age, 342 out of 832 parent respondents, which comprised 41.11% of the total population, had an age between 36 to 45 years old. On the contrary, only 64 out of 832 which comprised the 7.69% of the total population, had an age range of 56 years old and above. The result implies that there were more parent respondents were in their late 30s and mid-50s.

In terms of gender, majority of the parent respondent who participated in this study comprised 87.26% or 726 out of 832 parent respondents are female, this shows that mothers take more part in their children school activities their presence and guidance is highly needed during the blended learning.

In terms of highest educational attainment, 330 out of 832 parent respondents were college graduates with 39.66% of the total population. On the other hand, only 23 out of 832 parent respondents were in elementary level. Majority of the parent respondents have graduated high school and college. Further, it can also be implied that there are lesser elementary level participating in this study.

In the family gross monthly income, the highest rating is the income ranges from 30, 000 and above that is 32.69% or 272 out of 832 respondents. While the lowest rating in the family income that ranges 25, 000 to 30, 000 is only 2.40% or 20 out of 832 parent respondents.

For the occupation of parent respondents, the occupation "Vendor" is 258 out of 832 or 31.01% got the highest percentage. While the occupation "fisherman" got only 2 out of 832 parent respondents.

Table 2 shows the support of parents during blended learning. For the parents respondents on “Physical Support” statement no. 3 “As parent/guardian I monitor and do follow up for my child’s progress in MAPEH VI,” obtained the highest weighted mean of 3.28, with a descriptive value of “always” and interpreted as high level of support. The result implies that most of the parents do follow ups on their child’s progress in MAPEH VI subject to know that their child cope with the competencies of MAPEH VI subject.

On the other hand, responses for statement no.4, “As parent/guardian I make sure that I can assist in carrying out MAPEH VI assignments,” obtained the lowest weighted mean of 2.79, with a descriptive value of “Sometimes,” and interpreted as moderate level of support the result implies that most of the parents could not assist their child in making their assignments due to the different factors, it could be their schedule in their work or they are not knowledgeable on the topics.

Table 2
Level of Parents’ Support as perceived by Parents and Teachers in the blended learning
N=875

PARENTS’ SUPPORT		Parents and Teachers	Description
PHYSICAL SUPPORT: As parent/guardian I...			
1	review and check my child’s assignments before submitting their output in MAPEH	2.85	Sometimes
2	keep track of my child’s progress on.	3.29	Sometimes
3	monitor and do follow up for my child’s progress in MAPEH VI;	3.13	Always
4	make sure that I can assist in carrying out MAPEH VI assignments;	2.81	Sometimes
5	support my child on other extra- curricular activities in MAPEH VI.	2.89	Sometimes
COMPOSITE MEAN		3.00	Sometimes
EMOTIONAL SUPPORT: As parent/guardian I...			
6	spend time visiting school when asked by a teacher and willing to do work requested by the school;	2.96	Sometimes
7	reward or give incentives to my child for making a good effort in completing the learning tasks in MAPEH VI;	2.46	Rarely
8	encourage my child to talk about their feelings and problems with school work	2.74	Sometimes
9	attend the PTA Meeting	2.63	Sometimes
10	discuss the value of good education as well as my child’s future aspirations.	2.54	Sometimes
COMPOSITE MEAN		2.67	Sometimes
FINANCIAL SUPPORT: The parent/guardian...			
11	hire a tutor for my child to do follow ups for the lessons;	2.53	Sometimes
12	ensure that they have adequate cash allowance in case they need something for MAPEH VI lessons;	2.54	Rarely

13	provide internet access to my child for educational purposes;	2.47	Rarely
14	provide the basic needs for their child's requirements and projects;	2.46	Rarely
15	provide gadgets that can be used for research and communications.	2.47	Rarely
COMPOSITE MEAN		2.50	Rarely

However, a composite mean of 3.00 implies that the Physical Support of parents and teachers shows that the majority of the respondents perceived that the stated Physical Support are the things they usually do to support their child. Furthermore, the results agree with the study of Wilder-Smith, Chiew, and Lee (2020), relationships of parents' physical support and child academic achievement found that the strength of the positive relationships was consistent across grade levels. The increase of parent physical support associated with 6%-15% improvement in their academic performance.

In the Emotional support, statement no. 8, "As parent/ guardian I spend time visiting school when asked by a teacher and willing to do work requested by the school, got the highest weighted mean of 2.96 with a descriptive value "sometimes" and interpreted as moderate level of support. This shows that aside from checking their child's progress in school, parents extend their support in their child's activities in school when they are called.

While statement no.7 "As parent/guardian I discuss the value of good education as well as my child's future aspirations, got the lowest weighted mean of 2.54 with a descriptive value of "Sometimes" and interpreted as moderate level of support. The result exhibits that parents are not comfortable discussing about deep talks on aspirations for their child's future. Moreover, it shows that "Emotional Support got the composite mean of 2., with a descriptive value of "Sometimes." The result depicts that the parents are supporting the emotional health of their child to support their child learning during blended learning. In addition, it is supported by the study of Reschly et al. (2021), which shows that the family's emotional support positively influences academic achievement and MAPEH VI performance, among other positive outcomes.

In the financial support, statement no. 11, "As parent/guardian I hire tutor for my child to do follow ups for the lesson," their statement got the weighted mean 2.53 with a descriptive value of "sometimes" and interpreted as moderate level of support. This result depicts that in order to help their child in their activities and assigned task the parents hire tutor in doing follow ups for the lesson.

On the other hand, statement no.12, "As parent / guardian I ensure that they have adequate cash allowance in case they need something for MAPEH VI lessons." And statement no. 15 "As parent/guardian I provide gadgets that can be used for research and communications both got the weighted mean of 2.47 with descriptive value of "Rarely" and interpreted as low level of support. This implies that the parents do not give cash and provides gadgets easily to their child.

Moreover, it correlates with the study of Maclean (2022), learners showed higher academic performance whose parents are financially supportive and involve in academic activities compared to those parents who are less supportive.

Table 2 also manifests the parents support as perceived by the teachers, it also evaluates whether they have the same responses with the parents in Table 2. In “Physical Support” statement no. 2 “The parent/ guardian keeps track of their child’s progress on learning tasks,” got weighted mean of 3.39 with the descriptive value “Always” or interpreted as high level of support. The result exhibited that parents are concern on their progress.

On the other hand, statement no. 1 “The parent / guardian reviews and check their child’s assignment before submitting their output in MAPEH VI,” “Makes sure that they can assist in carrying out MAPEH VI” and “Support their child on the other extra- curricular activities in MAPEH VI”, got 2.83 with a descriptive value “sometimes” and interpreted as moderate level of support. The result exposed those teachers appreciate the various parent support in terms of Physical Support of parents.

In the “Emotional Support” as perceived by teachers’ statement no.6, “The parent guardian spends time visiting school when asked by a teacher and willing to do work requested by school,” got a weighted mean of 3.18 with a descriptive value “Sometimes” and interpreted as moderate level of support. The result displayed that most of the parents would not hesitate in coming to school when asked.

While statement no.7 “The parent/ guardian rewards or gives incentives to their child for making good effort in completing the learning tasks in MAPEH VI, got the lowest weighted mean 2.53 with the same descriptive value “sometimes” and interpreted as moderate level of support. Moreover, in can be seen that parents and teacher respondent have the same result as to giving of rewards and incentives to their child is least practice.

For the “Financial Support” the items got the same descriptive value as “Sometimes” and interpreted as moderate level of support, the composite mean is 2.52 with the descriptive value “Sometimes” interpreted as moderate level of support. The teachers perceived that the parents support their child financially in their helping their children cope with the competencies and activities in MAPEH VI subject. Hence, parents’ support being mentioned as having a variety of positive results such as increased school attendance, increased sense of wellbeing among learners, more positive perceptions of the school, and higher academic achievement. Parents’ support influencing student achievement requires recognition (Hickman, 2019).

Table 3
Level of Learners’ Motivational Practices in
MAPEH VI during Blended Learning
N=832

INTRINSIC MOTIVATION		WM	Description
1	I prefer MAPEH activities that really challenge me, so I can learn new things.	2.81	Moderately Practiced
2	I prefer MAPEH activities that arouse my curiosity, even if it's difficult to learn.	3.30	Highly Practiced
3	The most satisfying thing for me is trying to understand the content of MAPEH as thoroughly as possible.	3.23	Practiced

4	I choose MAPEH assignments that I can learn from even if they don't guarantee a good grade.	2.79	Practiced
5	I believe I'll receive excellent grades in MAPEH subject.	2.94	Practiced
6	I'm confident I can understand the most complex material in MAPEH presented by the teacher.	2.73	Practiced
7	I'm confident I can do an excellent job on MAPEH activities and tests.	2.40	Practiced
8	I'm certain I can master the skills in MAPEH being taught.	2.74	Practiced
9	Considering the difficulty of the classes, the teachers, and my skills, I think I can do well.	2.59	Practiced
10	I expect to do well in MAPEH	2.39	Practiced
Composite Mean		2.80	Practiced
EXTRINSIC MOTIVATION		WM	DV
1	Getting a good grade in MAPEH is the most satisfying thing for me.	2.58	Practiced
2	The most important thing for me is to improve my overall grade in MAPEH, so my concern is getting a good grade.	2.34	Not Practiced
3	I want to get better grades in MAPEH than most of the other learners in my classes.	2.37	Not Practiced
4	I want to do well in my classes because it's important to show my ability to my family, friends, employer, or others.	2.39	Not Practiced
5	If I study in appropriate ways, then I'll be able to learn the MAPEH lessons.	2.33	Not Practiced
6	It's my own fault if I don't learn the material taught.	2.38	Not Practiced
7	If I try hard enough, then I'll understand the material presented.	2.59	Not Practiced
8	If I don't understand the material presented, it's because I didn't try hard enough.	2.31	Not Practiced
9	I feel "disconnected" from my teacher and fellow learners in classes.	2.35	Not Practiced
10	I have strong relationships with fellow learners in MAPEH subject.	2.38	Not Practiced
Composite Mean		2.41	Not Practiced
Overall Composite Mean		2.605	Moderately Practiced

Table 3 manifests the learner motivational practices, the intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. For the intrinsic motivation, statement no. 2 "I prefer MAPEH VI activities that arouses my curiosity, even if it's difficult to learn," got the highest weighted mean 3.30 with the descriptive value "Strongly Agree" it means highly motivated. This explains that learners find some activities appealing to their curiosity and this boost their motivation. They are eager to learn even if the lessons in MAPEH VI are difficult to understand and perform. While the statement no. 10 "I expect to do well in MAPEH VI," got the weighted mean of 2.39 with a descriptive value "Agree" it means moderately motivated. This implies that the learners do not put pressure on themselves even they do not do well in MAPEH VI. In addition, composite weighted mean got 2.80 with a descriptive value "Agree" it means moderately motivated. This exhibits that the student respondents agree in all the statement for the intrinsic motivation and help them in motivating themselves to learn MAPEH VI during blended learning.

For the extrinsic motivation, statement no. 7, "If I try hard enough, then I'll understand the material presented," got the weighted mean 2.59 with a descriptive value "Agree" it means highly motivated. This manifest that learners should be encouraged by somebody for them to try hard enough so that they can understand the material presented. Meanwhile statement no.8 "If I don't understand the material presented, it's because I didn't try hard enough," got the lowest weighted mean 2.31 with the descriptive

value, “Disagree” it means less motivated. It is exactly the opposite of the statement no. 7.

In addition, the extrinsic motivation got the composite weighted mean 2.41 with the descriptive value “Disagree” it means less motivated. This shows that the following motivations are least practice. Moreover, this result can be related to the study by Vural et al. (2022), which found that extrinsic motivation presented a slightly weaker relationship to academic performance compared to intrinsic motivation. The intrinsically motivated learners persist longer, demonstrate achievements with their academic efforts and achieve more challenges when compared to extrinsically motivated learners.

Table 4
Learners’ Academic Performance in MAPEH VI during
Blended Learning
N=832

Grades	Description	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
90-100	Outstanding	136	16.34	3
85-89	Very Satisfactory	328	39.42	1
80-84	Satisfactory	310	37.25	2
75-79	Fair	58	6.97	4

Table 4 results clearly depict that most of the respondents got “Very Satisfactory” with the grades range from 85-89, obtained 39.42%. It can also be seen that there are only 136 out of 832 or 16.34 % respondents got the “Outstanding” with grades ranges from 90-100. 58 out of 832 or 6.97 % of the respondents got grades from 75-79.

Therefore, skills and competencies of MAPEH VI with four subject areas are difficult to master. Learners are encouraged to study and practice at home some skills and performance tasks in MAPEH VI subject.

In addition, it shows that even the learners are in blended learning, with the parents’ support and their motivation; learners can learn and can have Very satisfactory to outstanding grades. In relation to this result the study of (Wang, 2022) relates that blended learning significantly improves learners’ overall performance, particularly the cognitive domain. The effect of blended learning is impacted by the group activities, teacher, class size and intervention.

Table 5
Relationship between Parents' Support, Learners Motivational Practices, and
MAPEH VI Performance
N=832

Variables	Spearman RHO Test	Computed t-value	Tabular Value	Decision	Interpretation
At 0.05 level of significance					
Parents' support and learners' performance in MAPEH VI	0.677	19.198	1.962	Significant HO: Rejected	Related
Learners' Motivational practices and MAPEH VI performance	-0.0519	-1.499	1.962	Insignificant HO: Accepted	Not Related

For the paired variables parents' support and learners' performance in MAPEH VI, the Spearman Rho Test value 0.677 is less than the computed t- value 19.198 the result denotes that there is a significant relationship between the parents support and learners' performance in MAPEH VI.

Thus, it is supported by the study of Chohan and Khan (2010), which found that parents' contributions to their children's education have a consistent and positive effect on academic achievement. Consequently, parents must support and encourage their children to participate in activities related to the MAPEH VI subject.

On the other hand, the paired variables Learners' Motivational practices and MAPEH VI performance with the Spearman Rho Test value of -0.0519 is beyond the computed t-test which is -1.499, it results manifests insignificant relationship therefore both variables are not related. The result contradicts the study of Nawabi et al. (2019), which emphasizes that student motivation is crucial for achieving better academic outcomes.

Student's motivation has high positive correlation in their academic performance. There is significant relationship between school environment, structure and learners' motivation. Meanwhile, it is supported by the study of Vural et al. (2022), which found that extrinsic motivation presented a slightly weaker relationship to MAPEH VI academic performance compared to intrinsic motivation. This subject requires the learners' entire dedication and everything depends on their performance, which is measured through performance tasks.

For the paired variables in table 6 age of parents' to MAPEH VI performance the computed value is below the tabular value which is 16.919. The result denotes that there is no significant relationship between the parents' age and the student academic performance, therefore the null hypothesis is accepted. It can be comprehended that the range of age of the parents does not matter, what matters most is their support to their studies. In addition, it contradicts the study of Cantalini et al. (2020), which concluded that

age at parenthood affects educational achievement, particularly for children of low-to-middle educated parents. The study also found that children's educational outcomes tend to be worse when parents are significantly older.

Table 6
Relationship between Parents' Demographic
Profile and MAPEH VI Performance
N=832

Variables	Chi Square	Degrees of Freedom	Tabular Value	Decision	Interpretation
At 0.05 level of significance					
Age and MAPEH VI performance	0.8855	9	16.919	Insignificant HO: Accepted	Not Related
Gender and MAPEH VI performance	2.0707	3	7.815	Insignificant HO: Accepted	Not Related
Highest Educational Attainment and MAPEH VI performance	40.0572	12	21.026	Significant HO: Rejected	Related
Occupation and MAPEH VI performance	30.8589	18	28.689	Significant HO: Rejected	Related
Gross Monthly Income and MAPEH VI performance	40.6524	6	12.592	Significant HO: Rejected	Related

For the second paired variable the parents' sex and student MAPEH VI performance, the computed value is lower than the tabular value, meaning there is no significant relationship between the two variables, therefore the null hypothesis is accepted. Moreover, it can also be implied that parents' sex does not influence the level of performance among the Grade VI learners in MAPEH VI subject. Meanwhile it argues with the study of Sang (2017) indicated that parent's sex to affect learners' academic achievement.

For the third paired variable, parents' educational attainment and MAPEH VI performance with the computed value of 40.0572 is greater than the tabular value of 21.026, the decision is significant.

The two variables are related to each other hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Moreover, it can be implied that parents' who have higher education can support their children in their academic performance.

Thus, it is affirmed by the study of Khan, Iqbal, and Tasneem (2015) that high level educated parents to an extent, have more influence on their children to achieve and perform well in their studies. The assertion has been supported that high level educated parents usually show interest and care in their academic performance.

For the fourth paired variables parents' gross monthly income and learners MAPEH VI performance, shows that the computed value is higher with 40.6524 than the tabular value 12.592 has a significant relationship thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. Parents with higher monthly income can support and sustain the needs of their children that can be used during studies. Moreover, it is supported by the study of (Han, 2017) the results show that family income has a significant influence on children's education level and the increasing family income can improve their academic performance.

For the fifth paired variable, parents' occupation and MAPEH VI performance, the computed value is 30.8589 which is beyond the tabular value of 28.689 shows that there is a significant relationship between the two variables. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. It can be deduced in this result that parents' occupation can greatly affect the learners' academic performance.

It can be related with the study of Owuor (2022) that occupation highly influenced learners' academic performance. It is therefore, recommended that parents should serve as good role models to their children in their respective occupations so as positively influence learners' academic performance.

DISCUSSION

Findings

The highlights of the findings of this study are the following:

1. Demographic Profile of Parents. The majority of parent respondents are aged between 36 to 45 years, with a significant number also in the 46 to 55 age range. There is a notable gender imbalance, with a predominance of females. Most parents have completed college education, although there is a smaller group with only high school or elementary education. In terms of occupation, vending and farming are the most common professions, followed by government employment. Income levels vary, with many parents earning above ₱30,000 per month, and fewer in the lower income brackets.
2. Types of Parental Support. The study reveals that parents provide moderate physical and emotional support but are less consistent in offering financial aid. They "sometimes" review assignments and monitor their child's progress and "occasionally" engage in school-related activities. Financial support, including hiring tutors and providing allowances, is relatively rare. This pattern suggests that while parents are somewhat involved, their financial contributions are minimal.
3. Learners' Motivational Practices. Learners exhibit a higher level of intrinsic motivation, engaging actively with challenging MAPEH activities and finding satisfaction in understanding the content. They show less concern for external rewards and grades. Despite this, their overall motivational behaviors in

MAPEH VI are moderate. Extrinsic motivation, such as the desire for good grades, is less pronounced among learners.

4. Academic Performance. The performance of learners in MAPEH VI is generally high, with most achieving "Very Satisfactory" or "Satisfactory" ratings. A notable portion of learners also attained "Outstanding" grades, indicating strong academic achievements. This suggests that the blended learning environment has been effective in supporting high levels of performance among students.
5. Relationships Between Variables and Performance. Significant relationships are observed between learners' performance and various factors. Parental support is positively correlated with academic success. However, learners' motivational practices do not significantly affect their performance. Additionally, the educational background, occupation, and income of parents are significantly related to learners' performance, whereas parental age and gender do not show a substantial impact. This highlights the importance of parental involvement and socioeconomic factors in influencing academic outcomes.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher concludes that various factors significantly influence learners' performance in MAPEH VI during blended learning. The demographic profile of parents indicates that while most are relatively well-educated and in middle-income brackets, their level of support varies. Parents generally provide moderate physical and emotional support but are less involved financially, which could impact their children's educational experience.

Learners show a stronger inclination toward intrinsic motivation, finding satisfaction in engaging with MAPEH activities and understanding the material. However, extrinsic motivation, such as the pursuit of high grades, is less pronounced, suggesting that internal motivation plays a more substantial role in their academic behavior. The high academic performance of learners suggests that the blended learning approach is effective, although there is room for improvement in areas like extrinsic motivation.

Significant relationships were found between learners' performance and various parental factors, including support, educational attainment, occupation, and income. Specifically, parental support has a positive impact on students' academic success, highlighting the importance of active parental involvement in education. In contrast, parental age and gender do not significantly affect learners' performance.

In summary, while the blended learning approach has facilitated high academic achievement, addressing gaps in financial support and enhancing extrinsic motivation could further improve outcomes. The study underscores the need for a collaborative effort between parents and educators and suggests that focusing on socioeconomic factors and support mechanisms can enhance the overall effectiveness of blended learning programs.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. **Enhance Parental Engagement.** Schools should implement programs to increase parental involvement in their children's education. This includes organizing workshops and seminars to educate parents on how they can better support their children academically and emotionally. Emphasis should be placed on the importance of consistent physical and emotional support, as well as the potential benefits of more active financial involvement.
2. **Increase Financial Support Options.** Given the limited financial support provided by parents, schools might consider exploring alternative funding options or resources to assist students. This could include developing scholarship programs, providing access to educational materials and technology, and facilitating community partnerships to offer additional financial assistance.
3. **Boost Extrinsic Motivation.** Educators should develop strategies to enhance learners' extrinsic motivation by incorporating more tangible rewards and recognition for academic achievements. This could involve creating incentive programs that acknowledge students' efforts and accomplishments, and fostering a competitive yet supportive classroom environment.
4. **Tailor Professional Development.** Professional development programs for educators should focus on strategies for engaging both intrinsically and extrinsically motivated students. Training should also address effective ways to communicate with and involve parents in the educational process.
5. **Strengthen Support Structures.** Schools should consider implementing additional support structures for learners, such as tutoring services, counseling, and mentoring programs. These structures can provide targeted assistance and help bridge any gaps in learning and motivation.

By addressing these areas, schools can enhance the effectiveness of blended learning environments, improve parental involvement, and support students in achieving their academic goals.

Action Plan on Creation of Support System to enhance the level of Parents' Support and Academic Performance

Rationale

This post pandemic brought a lot of changes in actual daily living, more specifically in school setting which allowed learners to learn and acquire knowledge through blended-learning.

Furthermore, parents are by far the most important influences in a child's life. Their support plays a vital role at all stages of education. Parents' support and engagement in their child's education, both in early learning settings and in school, has a big influence on children and young people's confidence, achievement and attainment. The active support and empowerment of parents and can help create a learning community in which children and young people can engage positively with educators and their peers - particularly important as we recover from the Covid-19 pandemic.

In this view, the researcher proposes an action plan to contribute to the improvement and better understanding to the importance of parents' support for better academic performance of the learners.

Objectives

The implementation of the proposed action plan is geared towards the realizations of these aims:

1. To establish awareness to the parents' important role in supporting their children.
2. To suggest strategies to enhance learners' academic performance.
3. To discuss on how parents can embed opportunities for the academic achievement in their daily tasks in school.
4. To discuss on how parents help improve learners' academic performance in any learning modality.

Mechanics of Implementation

The proposed action plan in creation of support system to enhance the level of parents' support and academic performance of the learners during blended learning will be submitted to public school administrators and PTA federated officers for assessment, further instructions and approval.

Schedule of Implementation

The proposed action plan will be implemented before the beginning of the school year 2023-2024 and to be continued up to the succeeding years with the approval of the higher authority.

Evaluative Measures

The success of this program would depend on the cooperation of the schools' administrator, principal, teachers, parents and learners. Assessment should be done to correct and enhance some aspects of the program to ensure the realization and continuity of the program implementation.

Action Plan on Creation of Support System to enhance the level of Parents' Support and Academic Performance

Area of Concern	Objectives	Activities /Strategies	Person/s Involved	Time Frame	Success Indicators
Parents' Support					
Parents' Support	To assess the parents' willingness in supervising their child during blended learning	Home visitation	Parents and teachers	1 Month	The parents have expresses willingness supporting and guiding the learners during

					blended learning.
Help Desk Support System	To directly answer queries of both parents and learners.	Having a help desk personnel	Parents' and teacher	1 Month	Proper and good parent teacher communication
Governance	To orient teachers, parents and learners on blended learning.	Orientation	Administrator, teachers	1 Month	Well oriented and informed
Motivational Practices					
Trainings	To train parents to adapt in different learning modality.	Trainings and workshops in blended learning	Teacher	1 Month	Teachers' have 6to access to the necessary resources.
Necessary resources	To ensure learners have the access to the necessary resources.	Home visitation	Learners	1 Month	The parents have expresses willingness supporting and guiding the learners during blended learning.
School's Platform and Technical Support	To run and support the schools' platform during blended learning.	Having Learning Management System	School's technical support personnel	1 Month	The school has technical expertise to run and support the educational platform.
Help Desk Support System	To directly answer queries of both parents and learners.	Having a help desk personnel	Parents' and teacher	1 Month	Proper and good parent teacher communication
Content and Assessment	To have an appropriate content in providing lessons and proper assessment.	Regularly reviewing of assessment	Teachers	Quarterly	Complete and appropriate content and has proper assessments

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